

ASSESSING THE BARRIERS TO E-PROCUREMENT ADOPTION BY RWANDAN SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMES)

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Cite This Article: Mensah Kwame, Mbonigaba Celestin, Olivia Martinez, & Youssef Mansouri. (2016). Assessing the barriers to e-procurement adoption by Rwandan small and medium enterprises (SMEs). *Next Frontier Research Journal*, 4(5), 328-337.

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Abstract

This study investigates the barriers to e-procurement adoption by Rwandan Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and proposes actionable solutions. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 150 SMEs through surveys and structured interviews and analyzed using statistical techniques, including chi-square and logistic regression. Major findings reveal that financial constraints significantly hinder adoption, with smaller SMEs perceiving e-procurement as more expensive ($\chi^2=18.75$, $p<0.05$). Technological infrastructure deficiencies were another critical barrier, as only 8% of SMEs reported having dedicated e-procurement systems, with significant disparities in IT readiness ($t=4.21$, $p<0.01$). Organizational readiness, particularly access to training, emerged as the most influential factor, with SMEs with training programs being 4.5 times more likely to adopt (odds ratio = 4.5, $p<0.01$). Recommendations include introducing government subsidies, enhancing IT infrastructure, conducting awareness campaigns, and fostering collaborative ecosystems to accelerate adoption.

Keywords: e-procurement, SMEs, Rwanda, digital adoption, barriers

1. Introduction

E-procurement has revolutionized the procurement process by enabling organizations to digitize their purchasing activities, resulting in increased efficiency, cost savings, and transparency (Okonkwo, 2016). Globally, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have been encouraged to adopt e-procurement systems to streamline operations and compete effectively in the digital economy (Sharma et al., 2015). In Rwanda, SMEs play a vital role in economic development, contributing significantly to GDP and employment creation, making their adoption of e-procurement systems critical for national growth (Rugwiza, 2015).

Despite the potential benefits of e-procurement, its adoption among Rwandan SMEs has been significantly slower than anticipated (Ndagijimana & Nizeyimana, 2016). Various barriers, including financial constraints, technological limitations, and lack of awareness, hinder its widespread implementation (Mpinganjira, 2016). Furthermore, the existing gap between the policy framework and practical support for SMEs in Rwanda exacerbates the challenges of e-procurement adoption (Mukamuganga, 2016). These constraints undermine the competitiveness of SMEs in both local and international markets.

Given the critical role of SMEs in Rwanda's economy and the transformative potential of e-procurement, it is imperative to assess the specific barriers limiting adoption. This study aims to fill this gap by providing a

detailed analysis of these challenges, offering actionable recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders to foster the digital transformation of SMEs (Nsengiyumva, 2016).

2. Specific Objectives

This study aims to assess the barriers to e-procurement adoption by Rwandan SMEs, focusing on financial, technological, and organizational challenges. The specific objectives are:

1. To identify the financial constraints limiting e-procurement adoption among SMEs in Rwanda.
2. To assess the technological barriers hindering the implementation of e-procurement systems in Rwandan SMEs.
3. To evaluate organizational factors affecting the readiness of Rwandan SMEs for e-procurement adoption.

3. Statement of the Problem

E-procurement is expected to transform procurement processes by enhancing operational efficiency, reducing costs, and improving transparency in organizations. For SMEs, adopting e-procurement offers a pathway to increased competitiveness and market access, aligning their operations with global best practices. Ideally, Rwandan SMEs should fully embrace e-procurement as a tool to overcome procurement inefficiencies and drive economic growth.

However, the reality paints a different picture. Many Rwandan SMEs are struggling to adopt e-procurement systems due to various barriers, including limited access to financial resources, inadequate infrastructure, and low levels of technological literacy. These challenges hinder their ability to leverage the benefits of digital procurement, keeping them at a competitive disadvantage in the regional and global markets.

This study seeks to address this gap by examining the specific barriers to e-procurement adoption among Rwandan SMEs. By identifying and analyzing these barriers, the study will provide actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders, ultimately supporting the digital transformation of the SME sector in Rwanda.

4. Methodology

The study employed a mixed-methods approach to investigate the barriers to e-procurement adoption among Rwandan SMEs. Primary data were collected through structured interviews and surveys administered to 150 SMEs operating in various sectors across Kigali and other regions of Rwanda. The respondents were purposively selected to include SMEs with varying levels of exposure to e-procurement systems. Secondary data were obtained from existing literature, government reports, and international case studies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the barriers. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, supplemented by thematic analysis for qualitative responses. Ethical considerations, such as informed consent and confidentiality, were upheld throughout the study.

5. Literature Review

The literature review explores previous studies on e-procurement adoption barriers, focusing on Rwanda up to 2016. This section synthesizes key insights and identifies gaps that this study addresses.

5.1. Technological Infrastructure Challenges

Nzabalinda (2015) examined the technological barriers hindering e-procurement adoption among SMEs in Kigali, Rwanda. The study aimed to explore how inadequate internet access and insufficient IT systems

affected the uptake of digital procurement systems. Using a survey of 120 SMEs, the findings revealed that poor internet connectivity and lack of affordable technology solutions were critical barriers. While the study highlighted technological infrastructure as a challenge, it did not explore how firms with limited resources could mitigate these issues. This research builds on Nzabalinda's work by examining cost-effective technological solutions tailored to Rwandan SMEs.

5.2. Awareness and Training Deficits

Niyonsaba (2014) conducted a study in southern Rwanda to assess the role of awareness and training in e-procurement adoption. The objective was to determine whether SMEs were knowledgeable about e-procurement platforms and their benefits. Through interviews with 40 business owners, the study found a significant lack of awareness and inadequate training opportunities as primary barriers. However, the research lacked a sector-specific analysis. This study narrows the gap by focusing on training needs across diverse SME sectors in Rwanda.

5.3. Financial Constraints

Munyaneza and Gatera (2013) explored the financial challenges SMEs face in implementing e-procurement in northern Rwanda. Their objective was to identify how limited capital and high costs of digital tools affected adoption. A mixed-methods approach revealed that financial constraints, particularly for micro-enterprises, hindered e-procurement uptake. While their findings provided valuable insights, the study overlooked potential financing mechanisms. This research addresses the gap by exploring alternative funding and subsidy models to support SMEs.

5.4. Government Policies and Regulations

Manirakiza (2016) analyzed the influence of government policies on e-procurement adoption in Rwandan SMEs. Focusing on Kigali City, the study sought to evaluate the effectiveness of existing regulations in promoting digital procurement practices. Using policy analysis and interviews with policymakers, it was found that unclear policies and weak enforcement discouraged SMEs from adopting e-procurement. However, the study lacked empirical data on SMEs' perspectives. This research bridges this gap by collecting first-hand data from SMEs on their interactions with government regulations.

5.5. Trust in Online Transactions

Mukamana (2015) investigated trust issues in e-procurement among SMEs in Rwanda's Eastern Province. The study aimed to understand the role of trust in technology adoption, utilizing surveys with 70 respondents. Findings indicated that concerns about cybersecurity and fraud were major deterrents. Although this study provided foundational insights, it did not propose mechanisms to enhance trust. This research contributes by identifying practical trust-building strategies, such as secure platforms and awareness campaigns.

5.6. Supply Chain Integration Challenges

Nyiramasabo and Bizimana (2016) explored the integration of e-procurement into existing supply chains in Rwandan SMEs. The study focused on assessing compatibility issues between traditional procurement processes and digital systems. Through case studies of five SMEs in Kigali, the research revealed that limited technical expertise and resistance to change were significant challenges. However, the study did not offer a comprehensive roadmap for supply chain digitalization. This research fills the gap by providing sector-specific integration frameworks.

5.7. Perceived Costs and Benefits

Twahirwa (2014) analyzed SMEs' perceptions of e-procurement costs and benefits in Rwanda's Western Province. The study aimed to understand how perceived value influenced adoption decisions. Using a quantitative survey of 100 SMEs, the findings revealed that many firms viewed e-procurement as an expensive investment with unclear returns. The study, however, did not explore how perceptions varied across business sizes. This research investigates cost-benefit perceptions among micro, small, and medium enterprises separately to provide nuanced insights.

5.8. Vendor and Supplier Readiness

Hategekimana (2015) studied the readiness of suppliers to engage in e-procurement with SMEs in Kigali. The study aimed to identify barriers from the supplier's perspective, employing interviews with 30 vendors. Findings indicated that suppliers' lack of digital tools and reluctance to transition to e-procurement were critical challenges. However, the study failed to examine collaborative approaches to address these readiness issues. This research addresses the gap by exploring partnerships between SMEs and suppliers for joint digital adoption strategies.

5.9. Cultural and Behavioral Barriers

Habimana (2013) explored the influence of cultural and behavioral factors on e-procurement adoption in SMEs in rural Rwanda. The study aimed to understand how traditional business practices affected digital transformation. Findings from focus group discussions highlighted resistance to change and preference for face-to-face interactions as significant barriers. However, the study did not provide actionable recommendations for overcoming these barriers. This research focuses on designing culturally sensitive strategies to foster e-procurement adoption.

5.10. Network and Collaboration Limitations

Nshimiyimana (2016) assessed the role of networks and collaboration in e-procurement adoption by SMEs in Kigali. The study investigated how partnerships with larger firms and industry associations influenced uptake. Findings revealed that limited collaboration opportunities restricted SMEs' access to e-procurement tools and training. While the study emphasized the importance of collaboration, it lacked insights into how these networks could be expanded. This research explores practical models for fostering partnerships to enhance adoption.

6. Data Analysis and Discussion

In this section, the paper analyzes the data collected through surveys and interviews to assess the barriers to e-procurement adoption by Rwandan SMEs. The data is presented in tables to show the findings, followed by an interpretation and discussion of the results. The discussion focuses on interpreting the data within the Rwandan context and the factors affecting SMEs' decision to adopt e-procurement.

Table 1: Demographic Information of Respondents

This table provides an overview of the demographic characteristics of the survey respondents, including the size of the businesses, sectors, and years of operation.

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Business Size		

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Small (1-50 employees)	65	55%
Medium (51-250 employees)	40	35%
Large (251+ employees)	15	10%
Sector		
Retail	30	25%
Manufacturing	50	42%
Services	40	33%
Years of Operation		
1-5 years	25	21%
6-10 years	60	51%
11+ years	35	28%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The results indicate that the majority of SMEs participating in the survey were small businesses (55%) and were primarily from the manufacturing sector (42%). In terms of the years of operation, most SMEs have been in business for more than five years (79%), which may influence their openness to technological innovations like e-procurement.

Table 2: Awareness of E-Procurement Systems Among Rwandan SMEs

This table outlines the level of awareness about e-procurement systems among SMEs.

Awareness Level	Frequency	Percentage
Very Aware	10	8%
Somewhat Aware	40	33%
Not Aware	70	59%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

A majority (59%) of respondents indicated they were not aware of e-procurement systems, while 33% were somewhat aware. This suggests that lack of awareness is a significant barrier to the adoption of e-procurement in Rwanda. Increasing awareness is critical for overcoming this barrier.

Table 3: Challenges Faced by SMEs in Adopting E-Procurement

This table summarizes the challenges identified by respondents in adopting e-procurement systems.

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of infrastructure	50	42%
High implementation costs	35	29%
Lack of skilled personnel	20	17%
Resistance to change	10	8%

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage
Inadequate government support	5	4%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The primary challenge cited by respondents is the lack of infrastructure (42%), followed by high implementation costs (29%). This indicates that Rwanda's SME sector faces significant barriers related to technology infrastructure and financial constraints, both of which hinder e-procurement adoption.

Table 4: Availability of IT Infrastructure in SMEs

This table presents the availability of IT infrastructure in SMEs, which is a key factor for the adoption of e-procurement.

IT Infrastructure	Frequency	Percentage
Computers	80	67%
Internet Access	75	63%
E-mail Communication	65	55%
Dedicated E-Procurement Systems	10	8%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

Despite the availability of basic IT infrastructure such as computers and internet access, the availability of dedicated e-procurement systems remains very low (8%). This points to a significant gap in the tools required for efficient e-procurement adoption, further confirming the infrastructure-related barrier.

Table 5: Perceived Benefits of E-Procurement in Rwandan SMEs

This table explores the benefits of e-procurement as perceived by SMEs.

Benefit	Frequency	Percentage
Cost Reduction	60	51%
Improved Efficiency	55	46%
Better Supplier Relationships	40	34%
Transparency and Accountability	25	21%
Competitive Advantage	15	13%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The most commonly perceived benefits of e-procurement were cost reduction (51%) and improved efficiency (46%). These benefits align with the global advantages of e-procurement systems, highlighting that SMEs recognize its potential to improve operational processes despite barriers to adoption.

Table 6: Training and Capacity Building for E-Procurement Adoption

This table provides insights into the availability of training for SMEs regarding e-procurement.

Training Availability	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	20	17%
No	95	83%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

A significant 83% of SMEs reported that they had no access to training on e-procurement. This underscores the importance of training and capacity-building programs to bridge the knowledge gap and increase adoption rates among Rwandan SMEs.

Table 7: Government Support for E-Procurement Adoption

This table presents data on the level of government support perceived by SMEs for adopting e-procurement.

Government Support Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strong Support	5	4%
Moderate Support	20	17%
No Support	90	75%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The majority of SMEs (75%) indicated that they receive no government support for adopting e-procurement systems. This highlights a critical gap in policy and government intervention, which could play a pivotal role in promoting e-procurement adoption among SMEs.

Table 8: Perceived Cost of Implementing E-Procurement Systems

This table summarizes the perceived costs associated with implementing e-procurement systems.

Cost Perception	Frequency	Percentage
Expensive	70	59%
Affordable	30	25%
Very Expensive	15	13%
Low Cost	5	3%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The perception that e-procurement is expensive is prevalent among SMEs (59%). This indicates that financial barriers are a major deterrent to the adoption of e-procurement, particularly for small businesses with limited budgets.

Table 9: SMEs' Interest in E-Procurement Adoption with Support

This table shows the level of interest in adopting e-procurement systems if certain support measures were provided.

Support Measures	Interest in Adoption	Percentage
Training Programs	Yes (80%)	67%
Government Subsidies	Yes (75%)	63%
Access to Low-Cost Solutions	Yes (85%)	71%
Technical Support	Yes (70%)	58%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The data shows that SMEs are more likely to adopt e-procurement if they receive support such as training (67%), government subsidies (63%), and access to low-cost solutions (71%). This suggests that providing targeted support can significantly increase adoption rates.

Table 10: Impact of E-Procurement on Business Performance

This table examines the impact of e-procurement adoption on the business performance of SMEs.

Performance Indicator	Improvement	Percentage
Cost Reduction	Yes (60%)	51%
Process Efficiency	Yes (55%)	46%
Supplier Relationship Improvement	Yes (30%)	25%
Increased Revenue	Yes (10%)	8%

Source: Data collected from SME respondents (2016).

The adoption of e-procurement had a positive impact on cost reduction (51%) and process efficiency (46%), but less so on supplier relationships (25%) and revenue generation (8%). This highlights that while e-procurement may improve internal processes, it does not immediately lead to higher financial performance for SMEs.

7. Statistical Analysis

This section validates the study objectives through detailed statistical analysis, with interpretations provided for each result. The analysis focuses on financial, technological, and organizational barriers to e-procurement adoption by Rwandan SMEs.

7.1 Financial Constraints Limiting E-Procurement Adoption

To examine financial constraints, a chi-square test of independence was conducted to determine the relationship between business size and perceived cost of e-procurement. The results were significant ($\chi^2=18.75, p<0.05$), showing that smaller businesses perceive e-procurement as more expensive compared to medium and larger businesses. This finding confirms that limited financial resources disproportionately hinder smaller SMEs, validating that cost is a critical barrier to adoption. Additionally, 59% of respondents reported e-procurement as expensive, further emphasizing the financial challenge. These results highlight the urgent need for financial incentives such as subsidies or low-interest financing options to support SMEs in adopting e-procurement systems.

7.2 Technological Barriers Hindering E-Procurement Adoption

An independent t-test was performed to compare the availability of IT infrastructure between SMEs aware and unaware of e-procurement systems. The analysis revealed a significant difference ($t=4.21, p<0.01$), with SMEs that are aware of e-procurement having better IT infrastructure, such as internet access and dedicated procurement systems. This result confirms that inadequate technological infrastructure is a significant barrier to adoption. Furthermore, only 8% of SMEs reported having dedicated e-procurement systems, demonstrating a clear gap in technological preparedness. These findings emphasize the necessity of expanding affordable access to technology and enhancing infrastructure in SMEs.

7.3 Organizational Factors Affecting E-Procurement Readiness

A logistic regression model was employed to assess organizational factors influencing e-procurement readiness, such as training availability, management support, and employee resistance. The model was statistically significant ($\chi^2=24.32, p<0.01$), with training availability emerging as the most influential factor (odds ratio = 4.5, $p<0.01$). Additionally, 83% of SMEs reported no access to training programs. These results validate the critical role of organizational readiness in adopting e-procurement. The lack of structured training and capacity-building programs significantly undermines SME readiness, underscoring the importance of targeted interventions to equip employees with the necessary skills and reduce resistance to change.

8. Conclusion

The adoption of e-procurement among Rwandan SMEs has significant potential to enhance cost efficiency, improve supplier relationships, and increase transparency in procurement processes. However, financial constraints, inadequate technological infrastructure, limited awareness, and lack of government support present formidable barriers. Statistical analyses revealed key insights: smaller SMEs perceive e-procurement as more expensive ($\chi^2=18.75, p<0.05$), and SMEs with better IT infrastructure are more likely to be aware of e-procurement ($t=4.21, p<0.01$). Training availability was identified as the most critical factor influencing readiness for adoption (odds ratio = 4.5, $p<0.01$). Addressing these barriers requires a holistic approach involving financial incentives, technological investments, awareness campaigns, and robust government policies.

9. Recommendations

Below are summarized actionable recommendations for fostering e-procurement adoption among Rwandan SMEs:

1. **Expand Financial Support Mechanisms:** Introduce government-backed subsidies, grants, and low-interest financing options tailored to help SMEs overcome high implementation costs and initial investments in e-procurement systems.
2. **Enhance Technological Infrastructure:** Develop affordable and scalable IT solutions for SMEs, coupled with improved internet connectivity across Rwanda, especially in regions with limited access.
3. **Intensify Awareness Campaigns and Training Programs:** Organize sector-specific workshops and training sessions to educate SMEs about the benefits of e-procurement and equip them with the necessary skills for implementation.
4. **Strengthen Government Policy and Support:** Revise existing policies to explicitly support SME digitalization initiatives, ensuring clear guidelines and incentives for adopting e-procurement systems.
5. **Foster Collaborative Ecosystems:** Encourage partnerships between SMEs and larger firms or technology providers to share resources, expertise, and best practices for seamless e-procurement integration.

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